

Thermodynamics of Dissociation of BeSO₄ in Aqueous Solution from 278.15 to 308.15 K

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The pK values of BeSO₄ in aqueous solution determined from the e. m. f. measurement of cell

at 278.15, 288.15, 298.15 and 308.15 K are 1.977, 2.10, 2.225 and 2.37, respectively, and fit in equation,

$$pK = \frac{1759.21}{T} - 13.8798 + 3.4871 \times 10^{-3} T + 2.1398 \times 10^{-6} T^2$$

The ΔG° values at the above four temperatures are 10.53, 11.58, 12.69 and 14.00 kJ mol⁻¹ while ΔH° values are -16.21, -19.8, -23.49 and -27.5 kJ mol⁻¹ and ΔS° values are -96.2, -109, -121.4, 135 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively.

In this paper we report the values of pK of BeSO₄ in aqueous solution and the related changes in thermodynamic functions in the temperature range 278.15–308.15 K. pK value of BeSO₄ has not yet been reported in literature. Most of the compounds of beryllium are covalent in nature as Be^{II} having radius of 0.31 Å (in gaseous state) with no penultimate shell and screening effect has good polarising properties¹. Salts of tetrahydrated Be^{II} including BeSO₄·4H₂O are typical electrolytes. So the ionophore of BeSO₄·4H₂O after dissolving should dissociate in solution according to Scheme 1 and equation (10) shown below. However, Be²⁺(aq) ions are heavily hydrolysed². So for the determination of the pK values of BeSO₄, the following cell (C-1) was set up.

where, Q.H. represents quinhydrone.

Experimental

In cell (C-1) BeSO₄ and H₂SO₄ were taken in mole ratio of 5 : 1 and the minimum concentration of H₂SO₄ was 8 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ since at concentration lower than this Hg₂SO₄ might be hydrolysed³. Experimental solutions were prepared in double-distilled water having ionic strength <0.05 mol dm⁻³ strictly at the experimental temperatures. H₂SO₄ (S. Merck, G.R.) and BeSO₄·4H₂O (AnalaR) were used as such while Hg₂SO₄ was prepared electrolytically⁴. Before using the experimental solutions, they were deoxygenated by passing presaturated and purified N₂ gas for 10–12 h. Be,

H₂SO₄ and total sulphate content of the solutions were estimated by standard methods. The electrode vessels, bridge and the setting up of cell⁵ and the thermostat and potentiometer assembly⁶ were the same as described earlier. Duplicate cells were set up the e.m.f. of which agreed within 0.1 mV. The recorded e.m.f. values at 278.15 K (Table 1) are the mean of the two e.m.f. values (the values at 288.15 and 298.15 and 308.15 K are not tabulated for the sake of brevity).

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) as well as cell (C-2) studied earlier⁷ is given by equation (1),

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{k}{2} \log [\text{H}]^2 [\text{SO}_4] - \frac{k}{2} \log f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{SO}_4} \quad (1)$$

where, $k = 2.3026RT/F$ and $E^\circ = E_{\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Hg}, \text{SO}_4}^\circ$.

Earlier it has been found in this laboratory that equation (2) fairly correctly represents the activity coefficient f_i of ions in solution,

$$-\log f_i = AZ_i^2 \sqrt{I} - b_i I \quad (2)$$

where, A is Debye–Hückel constant (mol^{-1/2} dm^{3/2}) and b_i a constrained empirical constant (mol⁻¹ dm³) which is additive and reasonably independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere in dilute solutions provided the composition of ionic atmosphere is not drastically changed⁸. Similar idea has also been put forward by Bromley⁹. This means that whether we use H₂SO₄ alone or a mixture of BeSO₄

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TABLE 2

Temp. K	pK	$-B$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$	ΔG° kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\circ$ $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
278.15	1.977 ± 0.003	14.70 ± 0.02	10.53 ± 0.02	16.21 ± 0.03	96.2 ± 0.3
288.15	2.10 ± 0.01	11.1 ± 0.4	11.58 ± 0.07	19.8 ± 0.1	109 ± 1
298.15	2.225 ± 0.006	2.9 ± 0.2	12.69 ± 0.03	23.49 ± 0.06	121.4 ± 0.6
308.15	2.37 ± 0.02	4.4 ± 0.6	14.00 ± 0.09	27.5 ± 0.2	135 ± 2

are divalent, the product of the dielectric constant of the medium and the temperature decreases progressively with the rise in temperature leading to an increase in the value of the critical distance for the formation of ion-pairs. ΔH° values for the forward reaction (equation 10) are negative over the entire temperature range, slowly rising with the rise in temperature, indicating that the reaction is exothermic. In MgSO_4 , ΔH° value is constant and positive while in CuSO_4 it is constant but negative and in MnSO_4 it is negative, the negativity increasing with the rise in temperature over the entire range of temperature. So in BeSO_4 , ion-pair formation is endothermic. ΔG° values for the forward reaction in the instant case (equation 10) are positive throughout, increasing slowly with the rise in temperature, however the magnitude is the least among the four sulphates (of Be, Mg, Cu and Mn). This is due to fairly high negative values of ΔS° for the forward reaction (equation 10) over the temperature range. Negative values of ΔG° for the backward reaction (equation 10) clearly show the ease with which ion-pairs are formed, the more the greater the temperature. For the predominantly backward reaction the entropy change is positive, the value increasing with the rise in temperature. This again possibly conforms to the model proposed by Frank *et al.*¹⁷. With the formation of ion-pairs (having larger radii than either Be^{2+} or SO_4^{2-}) the primary hydration zone will be weaker creating a much greater area of disorganised water molecules in the secondary hydration zone. This will cause a net structure-breaking of the 'ice-like' tetrahedral structure of water leading to an increase in entropy, the effect increasing with the increase of temperature.

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